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KOPRA

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1 Introduction

The Karlsruhe Optimized and Precise Radiative transfer Algorithm (KOPRA) is a FORTRAN90 computer code for atmospheric radiative transfer modelling in the mid-infrared spectral range. KOPRA has been documented extensively in G. P. Stiller (2000). The present description follows, with minor adaptations, the text of the introductory sections of that document with the addition of a collection of subsequent relevant publications providing an overview of the validation as well as application of the program.

KOPRA was developed as a self-standing algorithm including all relevant physics for radiative transfer from the troposphere to the thermosphere as well as the instrument-specific response functions. It was dedicated to limb-observational observer geometries, though also nadir- and upward-views are supported with observers inside as well as outside the atmosphere.

As one of the first codes at that time, KOPRA was developed with the aim to be included in environments for retrieval of atmospheric state parameters, like temperature and trace-gas concentration-fields as well as instrumental features, like radiometric- as well as wavelength calibration parameters.

KOPRA models the mid-IR radiative transfer through the entire atmosphere (from the boundary layer to about 200 km altitude) and considers the relevant effects in this spectral and altitude range. It was a dedicated development for the data analysis of MIPAS/Envisat and is therefore especially suited for simulations for CAIRT which is envisaged to operate in a very similar spectral range as well as viewing geometry as MIPAS. The viewing direction of CAIRT is proposed to be close to meridional which requires to take into account the oblateness of the Earth for calculation of the line-of-sight, including refraction in a non-spherical atmosphere with horizontal density inhomogeneities. In this viewing direction, horizontal inhomogeneities may occur often, for example when crossing with the line-of-sight the vortex edge, the boundary of the innertropical convergence zone, or the terminator. Cirrus clouds in the upper troposphere, or, during polar night observations, polar stratospheric clouds may be in the line of sight. This requires the possibility to model particle-caused continuum-like extinction in the mid-IR spectrum.

Observation of the lower atmosphere down to the middle troposphere sets up the requirement of very accurate modeling of the absorption coefficients which has to cover all effects caused by high pressure, like pressure-broadening in combination of Doppler broadening (Voigt line shape) and pressure-shift of the molecular transitions, line-mixing (in particular for Q-branches of ro-vibrational bands of CO₂), duration-of-collision effects in the far line wings (water vapor, CO₂, N₂, O₂ “continua”), and a careful selection of lines contributing to the signal from outside of the observed spectral interval. In the lower to middle atmosphere a rather big number of “complex” trace species with high molecular weight contribute to the overall emission signal of the atmosphere. The ro-vibrational transitions of these species are too dense to be modeled line-by-line as it is common for other molecules. Therefore, methods to utilize absorption cross-section spectra provided by several molecular spectroscopy labs and provided for a (sometimes rather small) number of pressure/temperature conditions are included.

Further scientific questions to be investigated on the basis of the retrieved data further required to handle isotopomeric species of molecules (e.g. H₂O, HDO, and H₂¹⁸O; CH₄ and CH₃D; the

symmetric and asymmetric isotopomers of ozone ($^{16}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{16}\text{O}^{18}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}$) independently of each other and, thus, not to constrain their atmospheric concentration by a common profile.

In the middle to upper atmosphere non-LTE (non-local thermodynamic equilibrium) population of the molecular states will be a major concern for emission sounders. Therefore, the radiative transfer code must be able to handle the non-LTE effects in the radiance signal of the atmosphere, provided information on the non-LTE population of the molecular states is available.

In order to model the atmospheric signal as it is observed by a real instrument, the instrument response in terms of spectral resolution and apodized instrumental line shape (AILS or AISRF-apodized instrument spectral response function), field-of-view (FOV or SEDF-spatial energy distribution function) are considered.

Within a retrieval procedure or to provide a database for linear retrieval schemes like the LPE, KOPRA provides partial derivatives of radiances with respect to atmospheric as well as instrumental parameters. The link to such a retrieval concept with high flexibility is given by the analytical calculation of spectral derivatives with respect to an in principle unlimited number of parameters, with a user-defined and completely flexible set-up of geophysical parameter vectors and by providing the options to run KOPRA in appropriate modi.

The applicability in automated data processing is reflected in KOPRA's efficient and optimized calculation of atmospheric absorption cross sections, its user-defined accuracy adjustment and the ability to avoid recalculation of redundant quantities when embedded in a data processing loop. The user-defined accuracy-parameters control the calculation of absorption cross sections, the layering of the atmosphere, the mass integration along the ray path, and the accuracy of field of view and instrumental line shape modeling. However, the optimal choice of the accuracy-control parameters is not always obvious, and may depend on the actual case under investigation. This problem is accounted for in a dedicated study in G. P. Stiller (2000). With all these features, KOPRA reflected the requirements set up by the MIPAS/Envisat mission in terms of the instrument design details, the observation scenario, and the link to a retrieval concept with high flexibility. Given the similarity between CAIRT and MIPAS in terms of observation geometry, spectral coverage and high-resolution and instrument concept, the forward model is suited as a baseline to analyse CAIRT's capabilities and performance.

2 Contents and structure of the KOPRA ATBDs

In the following, we list the main content of the ATBD of the KOPRA code in G. P. Stiller (2000).

Part I

Reasoning for design of a new radiative transfer code for MIPAS/Envisat (limb-sounders).

Part II

Theoretical formulations applicable to limb-sounding radiative transfer (an update is provided in the CAIRT level-2 ATBD).

Part III

ATBD describing the geophysical model and atmospheric stratification. The quantities and variables which determine the atmospheric state in KOPRA are provided. It is described how the hydrostatic equilibrium is calculated and how horizontal gradients are taken into account.

Different possibilities and criteria for the atmospheric layering determining the radiative transfer discretization are described.

Part IV

ATBD describing the Atmospheric raypath modeling in KOPRA. A general method for the determination of raypaths as well as resulting path segments and partial gas columns within a layered atmosphere is used. No use is made of the gross spherical symmetry of the Earth's atmosphere. Hence, deviations from symmetry due to the Earth's oblate shape and atmospheric disturbances are considered directly. It is explained how KOPRA determines integrated path quantities like Curtis-Godson values, path column amounts and their derivatives. The inclusion of horizontal inhomogeneity into this scheme is shown.

Part V

ATBD of the optimized calculation of absorption coefficients line-by-line in KOPRA. The main problems associated with such an algorithm are concerned with line shape, the treatment of lines outside the spectral range of interest, and the way in which spectral sampling is performed. The solution to these problems as integrated in KOPRA is described together with methods improving speed of computation.

Part VI

ATBD of the treatment of line-mixing in KOPRA. KOPRA supports two different approaches, first, the exact treatment by means of a direct diagonalization method and second, Rosenkranz's first order approximation. In all cases, a parameterization of the relaxation matrix is calculated externally and read in by the code.

Part VII

ATBD of the implementation of the handling of tabulated cross-sections of heavy molecules and pseudo-lines in KOPRA. The cross-sections of complicated heavy molecules are calculated by interpolation of reference cross-section spectra rather than line-by-line calculation. For most species interpolation in pressure and temperature follows a summation of selected reference data weighted by the inverse quadratic distance from the target point in the pressure temperature plane. Additionally, for many of the heavy molecules a pseudo-line treatment is implemented in KOPRA.

Part VIII

ATBD on the parameterization of continua caused by gaseous constituents. The calculation of broadband continua caused by atmospheric trace gases like O₂, N₂, H₂O, CO₂ is described.

Part IX

ATBD on the handling spectral continua due to aerosol and cloud particles. Two possibilities for the simulation of a broadband continuum are described: the direct input of cross-sections and number density profiles or the calculation of cross-sections by a KOPRA-internal Mie model with aerosol size distribution parameters and refraction indices as input. The handling of analytical derivatives with respect to various particle-related quantities are described.

Part X

ATBD on the implementation of non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE) in radiative transfer. The necessary extensions for consideration of vibrational and rotational non-LTE are discussed in detail.

Part XI

ATBD describing the optimized calculation of the atmospheric line-profile and the Planck function in KOPRA. For the line-profile, an implementation of Humlicek's algorithm for approximating the Voigt profile function is applied in KOPRA and compared with several other implementations with respect to computational speed. KOPRA is especially designed for the calculation of spectral microwindows. Therefore, the Planck function, the non-LTE source function and the non-LTE correction factor for absorption cross sections are calculated in such a way that a given relative accuracy over the microwindow range is reached.

Part XII

ATBD describing how instrumental effects on the irradiated spectrum (apodized instrumental line shape, noise, field of view, spectral shift) are simulated by KOPRA. The calculation of derivatives with respect to elevation, spectral shift, ordinate offset, ordinate scale, and instrumental line shape parameters is presented.

Part XIII

ATBD about the calculation of Jacobians and the interfaces to retrieval applications. The simultaneous determination of the atmospheric spectrum and its derivatives with respect to various atmospheric and instrumental parameters is the basis for the use of KOPRA in retrieval processors. In this part the basic principles implemented for the calculation of derivatives with respect to atmospheric quantities are described. The derivatives with respect to instrumental parameters are summarized.

Part XIV

Description on optimized settings of model parameters. For the discretization of the atmospheric radiative transfer problem a variety of parameters are necessary which determine the performance of the program. An adjustment of these parameters taking into account the trade-off between accuracy and run-time is required for routine applications of the processor.

Part XV

The validation of KOPRA through detailed comparison with results from the Reference Forward Model is presented and discussed.

Part XVI

an assessment of individual forward model errors by disregarding a number of atmospheric properties and processes KOPRA is able to handle with, as well as an over-all error budget with respect to these parameters is presented.

Part XVII

provides an overview of KOPRA's architecture starting from the coarse structure up to pseudo-code including all subroutines with a description of their tasks. The main program variables are described. An overview of the module tree is presented.

Part XVIII

describes necessary input configuration and data files as well as output files.

Part XIX

lists all modules, subroutines, functions and exchange variables.

3 Collection of references

3.1 3.1 KOPRA: description

The main report on KOPRA as described above is the selection in G. P. Stiller (2000). Specific features are detailed in dedicated publications: Gabriele P. Stiller et al. (1998; Höpfner et al. 1998; Kuntz et al. 1998; Kuntz and Höpfner 1999; Hase and Höpfner 1999)

3.2 3.2 KOPRA validation

As KOPRA was developed especially for analysis of FTIR limb-emission observations of MIPAS-type instruments (MIPAS-Balloon, MIPAS-STR, MIPAS-Envisat) it has been thoroughly validated before its main application. First comparisons with the Oxford University's Reference Forward Model (RFM) were performed (Glatthor et al. 1999) as subsequently increasingly complex tests of ray-tracing, path-integrated column amounts, homogeneous and limb path calculations of unapodised, apodised and field-of-view convolved spectra. Also, physically more advanced processes, like modelling of CO₂ line-mixing, non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE), trace gas continua and cross-section spectra have been compared. All tests resulted in deviations smaller than the acceptance criteria. This test is also seen as an indirect circle-intercomparison with ESA's MIPAS Optimised Forward Model (OFM) for MIPAS-Envisat analysis which was previously compared with the RFM (1996).

The number of intercompared forward models as well as the depth of the analysis has been increased in the following years with a validation between KOPRA, GENLN2, Reference Forward Model (RFM), and Simulation Program for Infrared Radiative Transfer (SPIRT) for both local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) and non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE) conditions (T. von Clarmann 2002). Even more exhaustive comparisons have been performed within the EU-project Advanced MIPAS Level 2 Data Analysis (AMIL2DA). Here KOPRA and the models RFM, Modular Infrared Atmospheric Radiative Transfer (MIRART), OFM, Extended IROE Model (IROE1), as well as the Two-Dimensional Forward Model (FM2D) have been inter-validated (Thomas von Clarmann et al. 2003). Also in the framework of AMIL2DA, KOPRA's application within a level-2 retrieval processor environment was validated (T. von Clarmann et al. 2003). Here it was demonstrated that all the data processors under investigation (Retrieval Control Program (IMK-RCP), Oxford Processor To Invert MIPAS Observations (OPTIMO), Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt processors (DLR-a, D-PAC), IFAC's ESA MIPAS Optimized Retrieval Algorithm (ORM), Rutherford Appleton Laboratory's RET2D) were capable of producing reliable results in the sense that deviations of retrieved results from the reference profiles are within the margin that was consistent with analytical error estimation.

KOPRA has also been validated in its nadir-viewing mode within an line-by-line model validation initiative of EUMETSAT's IASI Sounder Science Working Group (ISSWG) in support of the IASI mission (Tjemkes et al. 2003). The study was performed to compare the model simulations with real observations by nadir-looking FTIR instruments and also inter-compare the simulations themselves. In total 13 different research groups participated with seven different line-by-line models. The results of that study indicated that in many spectral regions the models are capable of reproducing the observations to within the observed noise. It also identified some spectral regions with differences between the simulations and observations.

A more recent inter-comparison of nadir sounding line-by-line model simulations between KORPA, the Atmospheric Radiative Transfer Simulator (ARTS) and the Generic Atmospheric Radiation Line-by-Line Infrared Code (GARLIC), with infrared spectrometer data reached the conclusion that Lbl codes “seem to have reached a maturity in the implementation of radiative transfer so that the choice of the underlying physical models (line shape models, continua etc) becomes increasingly relevant” (Schreier et al. 2018).

Apart from modelling the gaseous atmospheric radiative transfer, the consideration of particles (e.g. aerosols, polar stratospheric clouds, polar mesospheric clouds) within KOPRA has been validated by comparison with the multiple scattering approach of ARTS (Höpfner and Emde 2005) as well as with JURASSIC (Griessbach et al. 2013). The latter also comprises inter-comparisons of JURASSIC and KOPRA for particle-free conditions.

3.3 KOPRA application

The KOPRA line-by-line radiative transfer algorithm has been used as baseline forward model at KIT and IAA-CSIC for retrieval of atmospheric parameters from infrared limb-emission of the heritage instruments MIPAS/Envisat, MIPAS-Balloon, MIPAS-aircraft, and the CAIRT demonstrators GLORIA-aircraft and GLORIA-balloon. It has also been applied for other observational geometries (GLORIA-aircraft nadir, IASI nadir and solar absorption FTIR), as well as for other instrument types and planets (e.g., NOMAD NIR spectrometer on board Exomars-TGO, OMEGA/MEx). KOPRA has been utilized in various ESA studies for performance simulations of the PREMIER IRLS instrument.

4 References

It is outside the scope of this report to list the several hundred scientific publications which are based on the results from radiative transfer modelling and retrievals using KOPRA (see e.g. the references at https://www.imk-asf.kit.edu/english/Publications_FFB.php and at <https://www.imk-asf.kit.edu/english/298.php>).

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